

GERMANY

UNIVERSITY OF LÜBECK

POLICY TO ADDRESS GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

NATIONAL CONTEXT

The basis for policies on gender-based violence (GBV) at German universities is the General Equal Treatment Act (AGG) issued in 2006. It defines forms of discrimination, explicitly including sexual harassment, and obliges higher education institutions (HEIs) to establish a complaints unit for any discrimination-related issues. However, the AGG only includes employees, not students. In addition to national legislation, HEIs have to comply with regional laws and can create their own regulations. At present, there are over 400 HEIs in Germany, and there are no systematic data available on how many have developed regulations on GBV (Kocher & Porsche 2015). According to a survey conducted among HEIs, 54% of participating HEIs had established a complaints unit for cases of discrimination according to the AGG by 2016 (Antidiskriminierungsstelle des Bundes 2020).

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

At UL, the policy mix relating to GBV consists of non-dedicated policies, that is, general policies addressing GBV as a part of the policy. Two policy documents dealing with GBV have been produced: The Operating Agreement on Cooperative Behaviour at the Workplace adopted in 2012 and the Guideline on Protection against Harassment, Discrimination, and Violence. The agreement is still in force but, with the introduction of the Guideline it became redundant for GBV cases. The Guideline developed and replaced many aspects of the former agreement.

The Operating Agreement at UL was first created as an indirect outcome of the participation of the university in a European-funded project on gender-based crime in the context of higher-education institutions. The Guideline on Protection against harassment, discrimination, and violence built on the ideas of the Operating Agreement in several ways. The Guideline on Protection consists of a preamble and 14 paragraphs and is divided in two parts: the first part is the General Section and it describes the scope of authority and duties of the university, the duties of members, associates, and guests of the university, the duties of the President, and the responsibility of persons in leading and supervisory functions. The second part (Counselling and Complaint Procedure) describes basic principles, the grounds for complaint, confidential support and counselling, counselling and company in the complaint procedure, the complaint unit, the complaint commission, the complaint procedure, measures, recourse, and the final clause.

URLs

- › Guideline on Protection against Harassment, Discrimination, and Violence: https://www.uni-luebeck.de/fileadmin/uzl_hochschulrecht/Recht_Universitaet/201105_RiLi_zum_Schutz_vor_Belaestigung_Diskriminierung_und_Gewalt_Ausfertigung.pdf

Entry into force: 2018.

TRAINING

The Central Equal Opportunity Commissioner has been trained to deal with issues of sexual harassment at UL.

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

Not specified in the institutional fieldwork report.

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence: The Guideline on Protection against Harassment, Discrimination, and Violence addresses two forms of gender-based violence: physical violence and gender-based harassment.

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Economic and Financial Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Physical Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Stalking |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Psychological Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Organisational Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Sexual Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Online Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Sexual Harassment | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Harassment | |

7Ps covered: The Guideline on Protection against Harassment, Discrimination, and Violence addresses **6Ps**: prevention, protection, prosecution, provision of services, partnership and policy.

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

Target groups

Academic staff
 Non-academic staff
 Students
 Other

Intersectionality addressed

No.

All target groups are addressed by the policy. Other groups have also been identified. The text reads: 'The guideline applies to guests of the University of Lübeck, including guest auditors, guest lecturers, and guest researchers, or those otherwise active at the university, as well as to trainees, scholarship holders, habilitation candidates, and non-scheduled professors.'

Specific vulnerable groups: The policy document addresses minors and persons in a subordinate position as groups particularly vulnerable to GBV.

Bystanders addressed: No.

Role of perpetrators addressed: No.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: No.

Monitoring: No. Monitoring is not addressed specifically in the directive but it is done as part of the policy review by the relevant unit.

Evaluation: No.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

The Guideline sets out a single step-by-step procedure for all, for reporting and investigation.

The policy defines: who to contact, how to report, the description of the investigation, a time frame, responsible persons/units, outcomes, and sanctions.

Who to contact: KoBAS (Conflict Counselling and Anti-discrimination Office) at the University of Lübeck, Complaints Office, Central Equal Opportunity Commissioner, Equal Opportunity Officers.

How to report: (1) Persons have the right to officially file a complaint with the Complaint Office and thereby initiate the formal complaint procedure. The complaint shall be made in writing or declared orally to the Complaints Office for recording. In the case of an oral statement by the person making the complaint, the employee of the Complaints Office shall record the complaint in writing and draw up a transcript of the conversation. The transcript shall be submitted to the person making the complaint at the end of the conversation for review and subsequent signature.

(2) The complaint must describe the events perceived as disadvantageous and discriminatory. Witnesses and evidence – if available – must be mentioned. The complaint should state which other persons have already been informed about the incidents and whether measures have already been initiated.

(3) After receipt of the complaint, the person making the complaint shall be informed by the Complaints Office of his or her rights, obligations, and further procedure. He or she shall be advised of support services offered by interest groups and counselling centres. The person making the complaint shall be informed that filing a complaint does not extend the time limit for filing an action of three months (in the case of any actions for compensation and damages pursuant to Section 61b (1) ArbGG in conjunction with Section 15 AGG). § Section 15 AGG). Other application or action deadlines resulting, among other things, from civil or criminal proceedings shall remain unaffected by this procedure.

(4) In the event that a minor is affected, the relevant special features of the complaints procedure shall apply in accordance with the rules of procedure of the Complaints Office. The Complaints Office will inform the person making the complaint of the exact procedure to be followed in such a case.

(5) The official complaint procedure shall be conducted in strict confidence. If confidentiality cannot be maintained due to legal obligations, the person concerned shall be informed of this without delay. The presumption of innocence on the part of the accused person shall be observed.

The description of the investigation: (6) The Complaints Office shall investigate the facts of the case. If the complaint proves to be well-founded, the Complaints Office shall inform the President, via the Registrar, of the result of the investigation and shall propose the next course of action.

Responsible persons: The Complaints Office, Presidential Board, President of the University

Outcomes: (7) If the investigation of the facts does not provide sufficient factual evidence for the existence of harassment, discrimination, or violence, the facts shall be submitted to the Presidential Board with a recommendation to terminate the proceedings and, if necessary, the proceedings shall be terminated by a decision of the Presidential Board.

(8) The Presidential Board shall decide on measures relating to employment law, service law, university law, status law, or examination law. If intervention is considered, the intervention will take place with the person against whom the complaint has been lodged, and only in an emergency will it take place with the person lodging the complaint. The latter requires the consent of the person making the complaint as well as the Equal Opportunity Officer and the Staff Council. The Presidential Board shall inform the Complaints Office of the outcome.

(9) The Complaints Office shall document all hearings and the established facts and inform both parties of the outcome of the discussions and reviews.

(10) If there are indications of facts relevant to criminal law, the President of the University shall file a criminal complaint.

(11) The rights of all parties involved to protect data, trust, and personal integrity and to initiate their own legal action shall remain unaffected.

(12) The rights of the Equal Opportunity Officers and the Staff Councils shall also remain unaffected.

Sanctions: (1) If students harass or discriminate against other members, relatives, or guests of the University or threaten or use violence, the President may initiate conciliation proceedings, issue instructions, and impose sanctions.

(2) Sanctions against students include, for example, verbal/written admonishment, exclusion from courses, account blocking, a (limited/temporary) ban from the premises, or, especially in the case of a final conviction or according to § 19 paragraph 4 of the Matriculation Regulations, expulsion.

(3) Sanctions against employees include, for example, verbal/written admonishment, a written warning, the transfer or relocation of the accused person to another workplace within the University, exclusion from the use of university facilities, termination with or without notice, and the initiation of disciplinary proceedings.

(4) In serious cases, the University of Lübeck is required to respond by (temporarily) banning the alleged perpetrator from the university premises and pursuing criminal charges.

This document reflects the situation as of January 2022.

Acknowledgment: *this vignette has been created on the basis of the work carried out by national researchers Monica Perez and Friederike Kressner in 2021, as part of the deliverable report D5.1 Inventory of policies and measures to respond to GBV in European universities and research organisations (2022). Available here: https://zenodo.org/record/5939082#.YfvXE_jTW5c*

